

Improved EfficientNetB4 Attention Model for Multi-Disease Detection in Healthcare

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Abstract: As the requirements are continuously growing for disease diagnosis, professionals and researchers are seeking better solutions. An efficient and successful illness diagnosis system is required to fulfill the needs of the present. Machine learning and deep learning are expected to play an important role in future clinical events, such as the diagnosis of disease. Researchers have proposed many single-disease and a few multi-disease diagnosis systems. However, most of the existing multi-disease diagnosis techniques are geared toward using electronic health records instead of image scanning for identification. In health care, the best interventions for the maximization of patient outcomes depend on early and accurate diagnoses of several diseases in a single model. Therefore, A novel and advanced multi-disease diagnostic system, called EfficientNetB4-Improved Channel Attention (ENB4-ICA), was proposed that allows an automated diagnosis, appending deep learning and transfer learning with a channel attention mechanism. This would allow pre-surgical evaluation in healthcare, support yearly medical check-ups, and provide for early intervention, especially in remote and rural regions having limited access to healthcare services. For the implementation and comparative analysis, a dataset of four different diseases, namely eyes, lungs, brain, and skin, comprising 28 classes, was collected. Additionally, the comparison of the proposed channel attention model is conducted with existing state-of-the-art deep learning models. The proposed ENB4-ICA model achieved a training accuracy of 97.75% and a testing accuracy of 93.75%, outperforming the existing state-of-the-art deep learning models. Healthcare providers may be able to save time and improve service quality by using the suggested innovative method.

Keywords: channel attention; deep learning; EfficientNetB4; healthcare; multi-disease diagnosis

1. Introduction

Healthcare is a vital component of societal well-being in the fast-paced, constantly changing world of today, as it greatly affects both the individual and the community's quality of life. In order to promote, maintain, or restore health, a wide range of activities is incorporated into the provision of healthcare services. These activities include preventive measures as well as acute and chronic care interventions. India has been significantly advancing its healthcare industry in recent times. As per the World Health Organization, the recommended doctor-to-population ratio is 1:1000. India stands out by exceeding this norm with a ratio of 1:834 ¹⁾. From 2014 onwards, there has been a significant rise of 112 percent in MBBS seats and 127 percent in postgraduate medical seats ²⁾. Even with these important advancements in healthcare, numerous patients still experience serious chronic illnesses that endanger their lives. Many diseases nowadays affect

human life, like heart disease, skin disease, brain disorders, and cancer, as these are the most common causes of death worldwide ^{3),4)}. Heart disease has historically been linked to the elderly, but in recent years, there has been a noticeable change, with an alarming rise in heart disease among younger demographics ⁵⁾. The risk that people in less accessible areas face is increased by differences in the accessibility of clinical care between populations living in urban and rural areas. E-health initiatives present a viable way to lessen the burden of heart problems by attempting to lower rates of disease, death, and related medical expenses ⁶⁾.

India's health system is changing quickly, and the country's rate of Coronary Heart Disease (CHD) is rising ^{7),8)}. The estimated prevalence of CHD among adults over 20 years old is 3.4 percent in rural areas and 8.1 percent in urban areas, which translates to a two-fold increase in rural areas and a six-fold increase in urban areas between 1960 and 2002 ⁹⁾. Another worldwide common disease, Skin

conditions, is a serious health issue that a large section of the Indian population suffers from ^{10),11)}. Patients suffering from skin diseases may experience severe emotional and psychological distress that surpasses the physical consequences. Growing self-awareness, particularly in young people, about their physical appearance exacerbates their anxiety ¹²⁾. Another recent disorder, the incidence of brain disorders in India, has become a major public health issue, causing high costs for individuals, families, and the healthcare system. Brain disorders include a broad spectrum of conditions that impact the brain and nervous system ^{13),14)}. These conditions can be mental health issues like depression, anxiety disorders, and schizophrenia, or neurological conditions like epilepsy, Parkinson's disease, and Alzheimer's disease ^{15),16)}. Almost 4.7 million Indians over the age of 65 have survived Alzheimer's disease, according to a World Alzheimer's Association summary of the most recent census ¹⁷⁾. They projected that 60 million people could be impacted by Alzheimer's disease in the next 50 years. Moreover, as per the WHO, about 60–80% of dementia cases worldwide are caused by Alzheimer's disease ¹⁷⁾. One person develops dementia every three seconds, with Alzheimer's disease accounting for 60% of cases ¹⁸⁾. Chronic respiratory diseases cause 3.2 million deaths per year, ranking third worldwide in causes of death, as stated by the data provided by the National Institutes of Health ¹⁹⁾. One major reason for the high mortality rate due to all these above statistics is the prolonged nature of conventional diagnostic procedures, which frequently involve numerous tests and consultations. This extensive timeline for diagnosis can be especially harmful for diseases that progress quickly, reducing the chances of receiving treatment in a timely and effective manner. This underscores the continued importance of timely and precise disease identification, as these illnesses can have lasting impacts on vital organs like the lungs, eyes, skin, and brain, etc.

Detecting these diseases early allows healthcare professionals to intervene promptly and provide treatment, ultimately leading to lower mortality rates. The combination of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML), and Deep Learning (DL) in the field of modern healthcare signifies a revolutionary change in the way medical data is analysed and healthcare decisions are made. These technologies have transformed medical diagnosis by using large datasets to detect complex patterns and provide precise forecasts ^{20),21)}. These models are able to analyse various types of data such as clinical records, imaging results, and genetic information, providing a thorough analysis that exceeds conventional diagnostic techniques. As we know, considerable progress has been made in predictive healthcare with the transition from single-disease prediction to multi-disease prediction ^{22),23)}. These models are able to evaluate the risk of multiple diseases at the same time, taking into account complex

interdependencies by utilizing DL techniques and large amounts of patient data. Furthermore, ML models enhance their predictive accuracy over time by continuously improving their performance through learning from new data. In the realm of predicting various illnesses, ML models have the special benefit of evaluating numerous conditions in different parts of the body at the same time, making the diagnosis process more efficient and giving a comprehensive overview of a patient's overall health. This feature is especially useful for handling chronic and complicated illnesses, where spotting symptoms early and intervening promptly are crucial for enhancing patient results. Moreover, the multi-disease prediction model can be applied in various clinical settings. It has the potential to help primary care doctors accurately identify various conditions, reducing the necessity for specialist referrals. In addition to this, it can offer diagnostic services in remote or underprivileged regions where there is a lack of specialized knowledge. The model can aid in large-scale screening programs by rapidly pinpointing patients requiring additional diagnostic assessment.

Therefore, the main aim of the research is to propose a novel ENB4-ICA framework for diagnosing and identifying multiple diseases. Different disease datasets of the eye, lungs, brain, and skin are gathered, and research is conducted to design an improved framework from images of various diseases. Most of the research already done by the researchers mainly focused on the diagnosis of a single disease, but the ENB4-ICA model provides a clinical decision for the multi-disease. This article is further structured in a subsequent manner: Section 2 provides an extensive literature review. Section 3 describes the research methodology, and Section 4 explores the outcomes and offers a detailed examination of the results. Section 5 wraps up the paper by summarizing the main results and possible paths for upcoming research.

The contribution of the presented study is summarized as follows:

- i. To propose an ENB4-ICA multi-disease diagnosis system that is proficient in classifying multiple diseases within a single framework with the help of an image dataset.
- ii. To increase the performance of diagnosis by integrating advanced DL techniques, including Convolutional Neural Network (CNN), transfer learning, and channel attention mechanisms, to improve feature extraction and decision-making.
- iii. To ensure the scalability and robustness of the system across various disease types, enabling reliable diagnosis for a wide range of clinical applications.
- iv. To evaluate how well the suggested model performs in relation to state-of-the-art models using important metrics like F1-score, accuracy, precision, and recall.

2. Literature Review

The literature review section offers a thorough examination of current research and approaches concerning disease prediction systems. This section aims to recognize important patterns, approaches, and areas of limited understanding by examining previous studies in the field. By analysing important literature, it paves the way for creating fresh methods and algorithms for diagnosing diseases.

Ramasamy et al. ²⁴⁾ suggested the Half of Threshold (HoT) training algorithm merged with Strassen's matrix multiplication technique to derive Strassen's Half of Threshold (SHoT) training algorithm. The proposed algorithm outperforms both HoT and Backpropagation Neural Network algorithms in terms of training time and efficiency. Ampavathi et al. ²⁵⁾ proposed a three-phased approach that includes: information normalization, weighted normalized highlight extraction, and a forecast to predict multi-disease. The Jaya algorithm-based multi-verse enhancement calculation utilized two meta-heuristic calculations to enhance the weight work. The proposed strategy was more productive than past strategies, and it can be utilized to foresee a more extensive extent of maladies. Men et al. proposed an Extended- long- short-term memory DL model that employs attention-based and time-aware techniques for multi-disease prediction. Using data from more than 5 million patient visits to a top hospital in Southeast China from 2007 to 2016, the suggested model was shown to be applicable. The outcomes demonstrated that, in comparison to multiple conventional and DL models, the suggested model does achieve better prediction performance. Anil Kumar Dubey ²⁶⁾ presented the combination of two meta-heuristic algorithms, namely the Lion method, and the Hummingbird optimization algorithm for the forecasting of multi-disease. The author used MATLAB to put the proposed approach into action by taking into account a number of diseases from the Kaggle or UCI repository, including cardiovascular disease, dermatological, thyroid, breast, lung, and Alzheimer's disease datasets. The suggested model outperforms SVM by 6%, KNN by 15.5%, NN by 8.3%, and DBN by 14% in terms of accuracy.

Buragadda et al. ²⁷⁾ proposed a blended model that uses CAT boosting and logistic regression algorithms. The model proposed transforms all the symptoms into numerical values to quicken the prediction approach. Results showed that this method outperformed the ensemble approach, with accuracy improved by +1.2%. Mohit et al. ²⁸⁾ worked collectively on ML algorithms to develop a technique in the health sector. Their potential and work underline the divergence of the doctor-to-patient ratio in India, and their research works as a bridge to fill this gap. By exploiting ML algorithms, the authors aimed

to assess the prediction of diseases, namely diabetes, heart disease, and breast cancer, that are globally recognizable. Their study findings bring out a good rate of precision in logistic regression and SVM in forecasting breast cancer. In addition, there is an ideal performance of KNN in finding heart disease. M. Alshmrani et al. ²⁹⁾ have focused on the evaluation of the architecture of DL, leveraging techniques such as CNN to attain a high accuracy rate and capability in disease recognition. They have conducted substantial research on DL for chest disease. Their work played up the value of large-scale datasets and vigorous models in achieving good outcomes. They focused on conveying crucial disputes in chest disease, including the accountability of DL models. Their research has improved precision and regulation, as well as the way they use AI in the clinical sector. Zhou et al. ³⁰⁾ contributed remarkably to the development of an automated image edge detection system. Their foremost step focuses on directing the restriction of existing technologies and instituting advances to improve productivity in disease diagnostics. They proposed a multi-view disease detection system. This system focuses on smoothing the way of disease detection by decreasing the dependency on manual operations.

Singh et al. ³¹⁾ have worked remarkably in the field of medical management with their recent study of the enhancement of the DL model. Their research differentiates the old CNN model from the modern and superior BFCNN model. They employ feature extraction and better classification algorithms to extract usable feature sets that decrease the dataset's feature matrix. The research presents a new method for categorizing diseases by employing a Bee-Featured CNN model. This revised CNN model integrates the actions of bee swarms to improve precision. The BFCNN model undergoes training and evaluation using medical datasets that include images tagged with relevant disease types. The proposed system shows promising results in the classification, but on a limited dataset. Diligent and accurate training leads to the success of the BFCNN model with a very high accuracy rate of 96.7%. In the future, they suggest the direction involving the enhancement of the BFCNN model for early-stage detection. Ibrahim et al. ²²⁾ suggested a multiclassification DL model for identifying COVID-19, respiratory infections, and lung cancer using a mix of chest X-rays and CT images. It was the first step toward establishing a single deep-learning model for the detection of a variety of chest ailments. The outcome showed that the VGG19+CNN strategy outscored all three proposed models.

Jiang et al. ³²⁾ presented a recursive mind information network that combined clinical data in view of first-request rationale with a repetitive brain network for the multi-disease conclusion. Eight models were assessed to check the outcome of the RNKN model. Not at all like different methodologies, this technique performs multi-infection

recognition as well as can make a twofold-class brain network by changing the objective SoftMax dissemination. Vijayalaxmi A. et al.³³⁾ made a demonstrative strategy to assess major well-being markers utilizing man-made brainpower models to conjecture future well-being troubles that might be used to direct preventive advances. Specialists utilized three AI calculations: Choice plant, Innocent Bayes, and K-neighbor classifiers. They demonstrated that various illnesses in patients might be anticipated by utilizing just basic center markers like weight record, temperature, beat rate, blood oxygen immersion level, and so on. Zhang et al.⁶⁾ introduced an interesting CNN engineering named Gathering Net to deal with the multi-mark constant infection grouping issue. The datasets comprised information from a neighborhood clinical focus, which contained 110,300 actual assessment records from approximately 80,000 mysterious individuals. The proposed strategy uses two multi-mark change procedures: the paired significance approach and the name power set technique. The proposed strategy beat different procedures with a precision of 81.13%. Having considered different researchers' opinions and their work, one can distinguish that there are many AI-based methods and techniques for diagnosing diseases in such areas as the chest, brain, skin, eye, etc. However, there is less research on how DL could be employed to classify multiple diseases under the same architecture using image sets. Therefore, the next part of this article describes the proposed approach to developing an early diagnosis of diseases within a single framework. Section 3 explains the developed model, and Section 4 gives a further discussion of the results.

3. Proposed Methodology

In the present time, computer sciences, medical sciences, and the healthcare industries are expanding and are inclined to cooperate with each other to encounter certain medical-related problems. These industries are implementing several intelligent technologies like AI, cloud computing, IoT, and other technologies that generate a lot of medical data, mostly in the form of signals, scans, videos, text, and voice^{34),35)}. Such data is being used and analyzed by researchers and medical professionals to develop autonomous systems that will enable early disease detection and the provision of appropriate care to save lives from life-threatening diseases. Thus, following the current research in DL and employing an understanding of how the approach can work, it is possible to attempt to create a model that can classify multiple diseases under a single framework with the help of image sets. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first model to classify multiple diseases within a single framework with the help of an image dataset.

3.1. Dataset Description

For the implementation of multi-disease diagnosis, data on four different diseases—the brain, eyes, chest, and skin have been collected. Data was collected from public repositories, and a total of 45759 images were included in the study (36,598 training, 4,598 validations, 4,563 test). Each disease consists of many classes inside it, which are mentioned in Table 1 with the number of images for each class. It consists of images of different types, like chest X-ray images, dermoscopic images, MRI, and fundus images, but the challenge included class mapping ambiguities and class imbalance (e.g., VASC <1% vs. pneumonia >15%).

Table 1: Dataset Description

Disease	Disease Category	No. of Samples	Sample Count Per Disease
Brain	Brain - Alzheimer Mild-Demented	1749	12481
	Brain - Alzheimer Moderate-Demented	1424	
	Brain - Alzheimer Non-Demented	2067	
	Brain - Alzheimer VeryMild-Demented	1495	
	Brain - No Brain Tumor	1630	
	Brain - glioma Brain Tumor	1382	
	Brain - meningioma Brain Tumor	1369	
	Brain - pituitary Brain Tumor	1365	
Chest	Chest - Covid19	1931	6840
	Chest - Lung Opacity	1600	
	Chest - Normal	1341	
	Chest - Pneumonia	1968	
Eye	RF - AMD	1725	14800
	RF - Cataract	1369	
	RF - Glaucoma	1678	
	RF - Hypertensive Retinopathy	1220	
	RF - Mild DR	1974	
	RF - Moderate DR	1969	
	RF - Normal Fundus	1984	
	RF - Proliferate DR	1295	
Skin	Skin - akiec	1506	11638
	Skin - bcc	1847	
	Skin - bkl	1958	
	Skin - df	1581	
	Skin - mel	1050	
	Skin - nv	1905	
	Skin - vasc	1791	

A sample of images for each category is represented in Figure 1. The collection of retinal fundus photos, chest X-rays, MRI scans, skin lesions, and CT scans of various illnesses was done using the open-source Kaggle platform ³⁶⁾. A comprehensive dataset comprising images in two main directories: the training directory and the validation directory. These datasets were structured to facilitate efficient training and validation of the DL model. The validation set was used to assess the model's performance during the training phase, whereas the training set was used to fit the model.

Fig. 1: Multi-disease Image set

3.2. Data Pre-processing

To prepare the dataset for model training, several pre-processing steps were undertaken. Images were loaded from the directories using `tf.keras.utils.image_dataset_from_directory`, with parameters set to shuffle the data and batch it appropriately for training. Each image was resized to a consistent shape of 160x160 pixels to match the input requirements of the model. Data augmentation techniques, such as random horizontal flipping and random rotations, and zooming, were applied to the training images to enhance the model's generalization capabilities. Afterward, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is applied to every image to reduce its dimensionality. It is required for slashing out redundant information and shifting onto the most significant features. Additionally, datasets were prefetched to ensure that data was fed to the model efficiently during

training, leveraging TensorFlow's autotune feature.

3.3. Model Architecture

The proposed ENB4-ICA model integrates transfer learning with a customized attention mechanism to enhance performance. We utilized the InceptionV3 architecture pre-trained on ImageNet as the base model, configured to be non-trainable initially to leverage pre-trained weights. Moreover, a channel attention mechanism was implemented to allow the model to focus on the most informative channels of the feature maps. Additionally, EfficientNetB4 was incorporated for fine-tuning, taking advantage of its efficient architecture and pre-trained weights. Custom layers, including global average pooling, dropout, and dense layers, were added to build the final classification model as depicted in Figure 2.

3.4. Proposed ENB4-ICA Algorithm

```

Input:
X: Set of input medical images
{ X1, X2, ..., Xn }
n: Number of images
C: Number of classes for
classification
Output:
P: Set of probability distributions
for each image { P1, P2, ..., Pn }
Pi: Probability distribution over C
classes for image Xi.
Steps:-
Step 1. Data Pre-processing
Augmentation, Normalization, Zooming
Xi@ = ANZ(Xi)
b) PCA (Principal Component
Analysis):
Reduce the dimensionality of each
image Xi:
Xi' = PCA(Xi@)
Step 2. 3D Octave Convolution:
Apply 3D octave convolution to
extract multi-scale features:
Foct(i) = OctConv3D(Xi')

```


Fig. 2: Model Architecture

Step3. 3D Normal Convolution:
Apply 3D normal convolution to further extract spatial features:
 $F_{norm}^{(i)} = \text{Conv3D}(F_{oct}^{(i)})$

Step 4. ReLU Activation:
Apply ReLU activation function:
 $F_{relu}^{(i)} = \text{ReLU}(F_{norm}^{(i)})$

Step 5. Element-wise Multiplication:
Combine features from different layers:
 $F_{mul}^{(i)} = F_{relu}^{(i)} \odot F_{norm}^{(i)}$
Here, \odot denotes element-wise multiplication.

Step 6. Concatenation:
Concatenate features from different layers or scales:
 $F_{concat}^{(i)} = \text{Concat}(F_{relu}^{(i)}, F_{mul}^{(i)})$

Step 7. Channel Attention Module:
Apply channel attention mechanism to focus on important features:
 $F_{att}^{(i)} = \text{Channel Attention}(F_{concat}^{(i)})$

Step 8. EfficientNet Backbone:
Pass through the EfficientNet architecture for efficient feature extraction:
 $F_{eff}^{(i)} = \text{EfficientNet}(F_{att}^{(i)})$

Step 9. Fully Connected Layers:
Apply fully connected (Dense) layers for classification:
 $F_{fc}^{(i)} = \text{FC}(F_{eff}^{(i)})$

Step10. SoftMax Classifier:

Apply the SoftMax function to obtain a probability distribution over classes:
 $P_i = \text{Softmax}(F_{fc}^{(i)})$

Step 11. Output:
Collect probability distributions for each image:
 $P = \{P_1, P_2, \dots, P_n\}$

Medical images are collected for brain and lung disease, including X-rays, CT scans, and images of eye and skin lesions for the implementation. Each image from the set serves as an independent input for the classification task. The total number of images is given by n, and each image belongs to the C possible disease classes. PCA is applied to every image to reduce its dimensionality. The output from this step is a reduced-dimensional image. The reduced-dimensional image is then processed through the 3D octave convolution layer. It is made to hold multi-scale spatial features by processing all the frequency components from the images. It gives a feature map that has spatial information among various scales. The feature map is further processed by a standard 3D convolutional layer. Here, detailed spatial features are extracted with the help of convolution operations among the three dimensions of the image. The output at this stage is a fine feature map. Next, the Rectified Linear Unit (ReLU) activation function is applied to the feature map. The activated feature map is joined with the previous feature map by element-wise multiplication. This operation enhances the important features and diminishes less relevant features. The feature maps are merged to create a new feature representation. It attains information from multiple layers, considering both low-level and high-level features. The feature map is then passed through a channel attention module. It assigns various weights to different channels of the feature map, which allows the model to focus on the most critical feature.

Fig. 3: ENB4-ICA Model Architecture (Block Wise)

This result is an attention-weighted feature map. Finally, the attention-weighted feature map is fed into an Efficient Net backbone. It creates a balance between efficiency and accuracy. It extracts the high-level features made to the final feature map. These features are then passed through the fully connected layers. It transforms the features into a vector essential for classification. A SoftMax function is then applied to the resultant vector. It transforms it into a probability distribution over the C disease classes. At last, we get a set of probability distributions $P = \{, \}$ which is used to categorize the diseases according to the images. The detailed description of the proposed ENB4-ICA model is presented in Figure 3.

4. Results and Discussion

In this section, the proposed ENB4-ICA model results are compared against various state-of-the-art architectures, including InceptionV3, EfficientNet, VGG-16, VGG-19, and ResNet. These models are tested on various sub-categories of brain diseases, chest conditions, retinal fundus, and skin diseases. The experiments were done in Google Colab using an environment with a free-tier GPU, which features an NVIDIA Tesla T4. The implementation was all done in Python using the Keras framework. The model was trained with a batch size of 32 to optimize GPU memory. The initial learning rate was set to 0.001 and adjusted through LRA (patience=3, factor = 0.1) for stable convergence. In the analysis, the main focus is on key performances like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score. Comparison among all is represented with the help of graphs and tables.

4.1. InceptionV3 Model

In the image classification task, InceptionV3 gained a lot of recognition due to its efficiency and accuracy. Developed by Google, this architecture is also known as GoogleNet Architecture. Figure 4 shows the results achieved from this model in terms of training and validation accuracy and loss. It is clear from the graphs that the model did not achieve good results on the multi-disease dataset.

Fig. 4: Inception-V3 Model Accuracy & Loss

4.2. EfficientNet

This CNN architecture introduces a scaling approach that adjusts the network's depth, width, and resolution, allowing for better performance and efficiency. With the compound scaling technique, this model carefully balances the three features of the network. Mobile Inverted Bottleneck layers and Squeeze-and-Excitation optimization help enhance the model's performance. Due to its lightweight and robust design features, it gives better performance in different computer vision tasks. EfficientNet base model results achieved on the pre-processed multi-disease dataset are shown in Figure 5. below.

Fig. 5: EfficientNet Model Accuracy & Loss

4.3. EfficientNet-B4

It belongs to the EfficientNet family. It provides a balance between performance and computational efficiency. The scaling method principle of the EfficientNet base model is extended in this, which uniformly adjusts the depth, width, and resolution of the network. It is a valuable tool for various computer vision tasks. This model is trained on the ImageNet at 380*380 pixels. It is applicable and recommended for cases where efficiency and performance are both critical. The accuracy and loss graph in Figure 6 shows the results achieved from EfficientNet-B4 for the diagnosis and classification of multi-disease.

Fig. 6: EfficientNet-B4 Model Accuracy & Loss

4.4. VGG-16 Model

The visual geometry group proposed this architecture, known as VGG-16, for its simplicity and effectiveness in image classification tasks. Its architecture consists of 16 layers, as its name depicts out of which 13 are the convolutional layers and the remaining three are fully connected layers. The attained results from this model are represented in Figure 7. Accuracy and loss graphs are represented in Figure 7. below.

4.5. VGG-19 Model

VGG-19, also introduced by the visual geometry group gained a lot of popularity in the field of computer vision because of its simple and effective behavior. Its architecture consisted of 19 layers having 16 convolutions and 3 fully connected layers. In this study, VGG-19 is also applied to the multi-disease dataset and results obtained from the model are represented in Figure 8. The model was able to achieve an accuracy of 65.1% after 15 epochs.

Fig. 7: VGG-16 Model Accuracy & Loss

Fig. 8: VGG-19 Model Accuracy & Loss

4.6. ResNet 50 Model

A DL architecture introduced by Microsoft, known as a residual network contains skip connections. Skip connects specialty is to allow the network to bypass one or more layers. A very deep layers network is designed in this like ResNet-50 and ResNet-152. This model solves the problem of vanishing gradients by the use of residual blocks. The results of this model are shown in Figure 9. The model was able to attain only 73.9% accuracy on the pre-processed dataset.

Fig. 9: ResNet50 Model Accuracy & Loss

By comparing the various state-of-the-art models, it concluded that there is a variation in performance among various disease sub-categories. For *Brain Diseases*: EfficientNetB0 got the best result in classifying Alzheimer's disease subtypes, especially in "Non-Demented" and "Moderate Demented" categories, with an F1-score of 0.76 and 0.91, respectively. For *Chest Conditions*: VGG16 and VGG19 were best in diagnosing COVID-19 and Pneumonia, with F1-scores above 0.85 in both cases. Efficient Net used in detecting Lung Opacity, with f1-scores near 0.86. For *Retinal Fundus Diseases*: VGG19 showed good results in classifying cataracts and Glaucoma, with F1-scores of 0.90 and 0.68, respectively. The VGG models outperformed all other models in this category. For *Skin Diseases*: VGG16 and EfficientNetB4 were effective in achieving high F1-scores for this

condition. VGG16 was prominent in detecting melanoma and benign tumors, with F1-scores near to 0.85. EfficientNetB4 worked well in distinguishing various skin problems, which showed its high accuracy in this classification.

Now, according to the analysis of state-of-the-art models, no single model was consistently better than any other for all types of diseases, even though some models perform exceptionally well in particular categories. This indicates how crucial it is to choose a model that is appropriate for the specific medical issue under study. EfficientNet-B4 consistently outperformed other models due to its compound scaling and lightweight architecture, and makes more efficient use of model parameters.

4.7. Proposed EfficientNetB4-Improved Channel Attention (ENB4-ICA) Model

An ENB4-ICA model proposed in this study undergoes a training process that involves 15 epochs, with accuracy and loss monitored for both training and validation sets denoted in Figure 10. The model achieved substantial accuracy improvements over epochs, demonstrating the effectiveness of the data augmentation and transfer learning strategies. Training accuracy consistently improved over epochs, indicating effective learning from the augmented training data, while validation accuracy showed stable improvement, confirming the model's generalization capability.

Fig. 10: Accuracy and Loss for Training and Validation

Fig. 11: Confusion matrix on the test dataset for the Multi-Disease prediction model

The architecture, combining InceptionV3 and EfficientNetB4 with a channel attention mechanism, demonstrated robust performance across multiple metrics. It achieved high precision, indicating accurate positive predictions, and maintained strong recall, capturing a high proportion of true positives. Additionally, the model balanced precision and recall effectively, resulting in a high F1 score. This is represented by the confusion matrix

in Figure 11 and the classification report presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Classification Report

Class Label	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Brain - Alzheimer MildDemented	0.98	0.96	0.97	176

Brain - Alzheimer ModerateDemented	1	1	1	143
Brain - Alzheimer NonDemented	0.98	0.88	0.93	208
Brain - Alzheimer VeryMildDemented	0.83	0.97	0.89	150
Brain - No Brain Tumor	1	1	1	163
Brain - glioma Brain Tumor	1	0.99	0.99	139
Brain - meningioma Brain Tumor	0.97	1	0.99	138
Brain - pituitary Brain Tumor	1	0.99	0.99	137
Chest - Covid19	0.99	0.98	0.99	194
Chest - Lung Opacity	0.98	0.99	0.98	160
Chest - Normal	0.97	1	0.99	135
Chest - Pneumonia	1	0.98	0.99	198
RF - AMD	0.94	0.98	0.96	173
RF - Cataract	0.99	1	1	138
RF - Glaucoma	0.98	0.93	0.95	169
RF - Hypertensive Retinopathy	0.96	0.95	0.95	122
RF - Mild DR	0.71	0.74	0.72	198
RF - Moderate DR	0.72	0.69	0.7	198
RF - Normal Fundus	0.99	1	1	199
RF - Proliferate DR	0.92	0.79	0.85	130
RF - Severe DR	0.86	0.94	0.9	160
Skin - akiec	0.95	1	0.97	152
Skin - bcc	0.98	1	0.99	186
Skin - bkl	0.95	0.88	0.91	197
Skin - df	1	1	1	159
Skin - mel	0.74	0.69	0.71	105
Skin - nv	0.88	0.92	0.9	191
Skin - vasc	1	1	1	180
Accuracy		0.94		4598
Macro Avg	0.94	0.94	0.94	4598
Weighted Avg	0.94	0.94	0.94	4598

Also, Figure 12 shows the error by class on the test dataset. However, despite the above facts, the model, which was proposed in this paper, did have a good training as well as testing accuracy, but still, the model fails to learn some specific classes, for example, RF-Moderate DR, RF-Mild DR, etc.

Further, to evaluate the proposed ENB4-ICA model's performance, a comparative analysis with several baseline models has been conducted. The inclusion of the channel attention mechanism and transfer learning with EfficientNetB4 yielded superior results in terms of accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score compared to traditional CNN architectures. Results are shown in Table 3.

Fig. 12: Error by class on the test data set

By critically analyzing the results, some gaps, such as less diversity in the dataset, generalizability, or inadequate clinical evaluation, have been identified, which may need further investigation.

4.8. Sustainability Metrics of ENB4-ICA

The ENB4-ICA model promotes sustainability by enhancing societal and economic dimensions in healthcare research and application. It ensures accessibility and efficiency, delivering fast and accurate multi-disease diagnoses, particularly in resource-limited areas. Economically, it reduces infrastructure and operational costs, making it more cost-effective than traditional systems. Its scalability and adaptability can enable widespread deployment, supporting sustainable healthcare practices.

Table 3: Model Evaluation Results

Model	Epochs	Training		Validation		Testing		Precision	Recall	F1 Score
		Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy	Loss	Accuracy	Loss			
Inception-V3	15	0.4889	3.6319	0.5331	2.4541	0.5647	2.4448	0.55	0.55	0.52
Efficient-Net		0.7113	0.7477	0.7044	0.7582	0.7388	0.6931	0.75	0.72	0.72
EfficientNet-B4		0.6884	0.8182	0.6807	0.8373	0.7109	0.7766	0.73	0.7	0.7
VGG-16		0.6579	0.8981	0.6766	0.8338	0.6819	0.8086	0.69	0.66	0.67
VGG-19		0.6514	0.9112	0.6646	0.8678	0.6841	0.8384	0.71	0.68	0.67
ResNet-50		0.739	0.6508	0.7265	0.6893	0.7287	0.6624	0.77	0.74	0.72
Proposed ENB4-ICA		0.9775	0.258	0.9322	0.3753	0.9375	0.4232	0.94	0.94	0.94

5. Conclusion and Future Scope

In this study, a DL model was designed and evaluated for multi-disease prediction and classification of various diseases, including those affecting the chest, brain, skin, and eyes. A novel ENB4-ICA model is implemented to classify other stages of diseases of the mentioned types for early diagnosis and to start the treatment of the diseases timely. To the best of our knowledge, this may be the first model to classify multiple diseases within a single framework with the help of an image dataset. In the proposed ENB4-ICA model, the Efficient-Net architecture has been used for the classification, along with the use of transfer learning and channel attention concepts. The proposed Efficient-Net channel attention model demonstrated competitive performance on the image dataset of the four disease categories with 28 sub-classes. The ENB4-ICA model achieved a training accuracy of 97.75% and a testing accuracy of 93.75% in only fifteen epochs. A comparison of the ENB4-ICA model with the existing state-of-the-art models, such as Inception-V3, EfficientNet, EfficientNet-B4, VGG-16, VGG-19, and ResNet-50, has been demonstrated, and it is concluded that these existing models attained a low accuracy rate and higher error by class. However, the ENB4-ICA model overcomes all these issues by achieving a higher accuracy rate, nevertheless, it is still limited to classifying only 28 disease subclasses, excluding other modalities like clinical signals or reports. But, the model's high accuracy and capacity to diagnose multi-disease may support healthcare professionals in making an accurate and timely diagnosis, and a possible solution for distant and resource-constrained areas ultimately enhancing patient outcomes. Furthermore, the model developed in this work can be used in real-world settings for an intelligent clinical decision support system. Adding more diseases and their subclasses to the intended output space will be a significant future area for this effort. Signals or electronic data can also be incorporated for multi-disease diagnosis to generalize the model. Moreover, research should also include developing scalable, robust models that perform well in different populations and settings while providing answers to data privacy and integration, responding to future requirements.

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Nomenclature

ENB4-ICA	EfficientNetB4-Improved Attention	Channel
AI	Artificial Intelligence	
ML	Machine Learning	
DL	Deep Learning	

CHD	Coronary Heart Disease
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
ReLU	Rectified Linear Unit
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network

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